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1. Introduction

The number and diversity of applications of fibre-reinforced polymers (FRPs) have increased remarkably, especially in leading technological sectors like aeronautics and space, where carbon/epoxy systems are currently widespread. However, thermoplastic composites are increasingly gaining relevance, not only on high throughput industries such as the automotive, but also on the previously mentioned leading technological sectors such as aeronautics.

With the introduction of new materials, such as thermoplastic composites, in primary structure applications such as aeronautics, comes the need for characterisation of their mechanical response to support the design of structures made with these materials. In the case of aerostructures, this response must be assessed by means of a “building-block” approach (Figure 1) consisting of a large number of physical tests, required to have a reliable statistical representation of the structural performance of the material. This causes the introduction of new materials in the aeronautic sector to be complex, costly and extremely time consuming. The possibility to totally or partially replace and complement by simulation (or *virtual testing*) the physical tests at the levels above the material characterisation level is, therefore, of great interest.

Figure 1 Virtual testing pyramid.

However, the introduction of new materials also requires the adoption of appropriate constitutive models to represent, by simulation, their elastic, inelastic, time and environmental response, as, otherwise, the replacement of the physical tests by simulation will be compromised. The formulation of such appropriate constitutive models demands, on the other hand, a deep knowledge of the mechanical response of the class of materials being introduced. In the case of thermoplastic composites, the following aspects should be considered for a detailed and accurate representation of the mechanical behaviour of this class of composite materials:

- processing conditions – composite consolidation and degree of crystallinity of the thermoplastic matrix;
- anisotropic time-dependent pre-localisation nonlinear behaviour – directional viscoelasticity and viscoplasticity;
- anisotropic (time-dependent) post-localisation inelastic behaviour – anisotropic damage and fracture;
- temperature-dependent behaviour.

This report addresses the current state-of-art concerning the mechanical response of advanced thermoplastic composites, its most influencing aspects, and the modelling strategies adopted.

2. Mechanical behaviour of thermoplastic-based composites

Although the first comprehensive studies about the mechanical behaviour of thermoplastic-based composites date back to the late 80's, the most recent structural and environmental requisites of the mobility industry, related with energy consumption – hence, weight and shape – and end-of-life requirements, led to an increased interest in this class of composite materials in the last years as an alternative to thermoset-based composites due to their attractive mechanical properties, welding capability, rapid processing, flexibility in forming and manufacturing, and recyclability. However, the mechanical behaviour of thermoplastic-based composites can be substantially different from their thermoset counterparts. An important aspect influencing the mechanical properties of thermoplastic-based composites is the choice of the processing conditions.

The mechanical properties of semi-crystalline thermoplastic materials are strongly linked, among other factors, with their degree of crystallinity, which is known to decrease with increasing cooling rate. For example, in the case of poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK), increasing cooling rates – lower degrees of crystallinity – lead to strong reductions in tensile strength and modulus, and a remarkable increase in ductility (Gao & Kim, 2000). Consequently, the cooling rate of the thermoplastic-based composite will have an important effect on its mechanical behaviour, especially on its matrix-dominated properties.

This is observed, for instance, on delamination resistance. Higher processing temperatures and slower cooling rates are required to obtain carbon fibre-reinforced PEEK laminates with higher interlaminar fracture toughness at initiation (Jar & Kausch, 1994). The same is true for the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and fibre/matrix interfacial shear strength; the higher the cooling rate is, the lower is the degree of crystallinity of the PEEK matrix, and consequently the lower is the ILSS and the fibre/matrix interfacial shear strength (Gao & Kim, 2000).

Consolidation also strongly affects the delamination resistance of thermoplastic-based composites. If no pressure is applied during the heating and holding (forming) stages of the process, consolidation is not effective, and the layers become weakly bonded (Jar & Kausch, 1994). This is attributed to trapped air that can remain at the interlaminar regions, leading to large voids and thick, weak resin-rich interlaminar regions (Jar & Kausch, 1994).

In addition to the processing conditions, thermoplastic polymers are characterised by a rather complex time- and temperature-dependent nonlinear behaviour. For instance, temperature (El-Qoubaa & Othman, 2016) and strain rate (El-Qoubaa & Othman, 2015) are known to have a strong effect on the material properties of PEEK. While the tensile and compressive yield stresses and the elastic modulus decrease with increasing temperature, the tensile and compressive yield stresses increase with strain rate (Rae, et al., 2007).

In the case of fibre-reinforced PEEK, it is observed that the elastic moduli and the strength also decrease with increasing temperature, the latter in a greater extent (Sun & Rui, 1990). In fact, the transverse, matrix-dominated moduli and strengths are particularly sensitive to the temperature (Yoon & Sun, 1991), as well as the strain rate, increasing with the latter (Yoon & Sun, 1991). Moreover, mode II interlaminar fracture tests showed that carbon fibre-reinforced PEEK exhibits ductile crack growth at low loading rates, but brittle crack growth at high rates, with a reduction of the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness up to 80% for moderate loading rates (Smiley & Pipes, 1987). The effect on the intralaminar fracture toughness has, however, not been studied yet. It is, nevertheless, clear that models for the prediction of the behaviour of thermoplastic composites should account for these viscous effects in the elastic and plastic domains prior to damage initiation, coupling both the viscoelastic and viscoplastic modes of deformation, and in the inelastic domain after damage initiation.

Finally, it should be stressed that these observations have been so far focused on PEEK composites. It is, however, not clear whether these effects and their extent remain the same for other high performance semi-crystalline thermoplastic matrices (e.g. poly-ether-ketone-ketone (PEKK)). Hence, verification and characterisation of these effects need to be performed on other thermoplastic composite systems, including the effect on the mechanical response of the manufacturing conditions (viz. consolidation and cooling rate) and loading rate. This will require, in addition to accurate virtual testing platforms, detailed physical characterisation at the coupon and element levels, including tests on specimens manufactured with different process conditions and at different strain rates.

3. Analysis models for thermoplastic-based composites

Considering that thermoplastic-based composites present a marked viscous behaviour, strain rate effects must be captured by advanced constitutive models. Such models enable a reduction of safety factors when designing new parts, and enable the use of less material, which results in weight savings.

Recent work has been performed in modelling these viscous effects (Garcia-Gonzalez, et al., 2017) based on earlier experimental observations (Rae, et al., 2007), however limited to the neat thermoplastic material, not the fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composite.

To model the viscous elastic-plastic behaviour of thermoplastic-based composites, appropriate models should be developed, that account for the transverse isotropy (in case of unidirectional composites) or orthotropy (in case of multidirectional fabrics) introduced by the fibrous reinforcement.

One of the first contributions for the plastic behaviour of fibre-reinforced composites proposed a simple flow rule for orthotropic plasticity, assuming a plane stress state, and applied to off-axis tensile loading of unidirectional laminae (Sun & Chen, 1989). Later, a quadratic plastic potential associated with an isotropic hardening and an associated flow rule was proposed, assuming that uniform dilatational strains do not contribute to plastic deformation and ignoring plastic deformation in the fibre direction (Chen & Sun, 1993). The necessary elastic constants to formulate the plastic potential were determined using a micro-mechanical model based on a representative volume element. However, viscous effects were not accounted for.

More recently, a fully three-dimensional elastic-plastic model for unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites relying on the invariant theory – the mathematical framework that enables the representation of anisotropy using isotropic tensorial functions – was proposed and validated (Vogler, et al., 2013), exhibiting good accuracy. Using such framework, the formulation can be the same regardless of the orientation angle of the fibres. However, this model did not account for the viscous effects.

Other contributions focused on the nonlinear behaviour up to and including the failure of single unidirectional and cross-ply layers of laminated composites (Vaziri, et al., 1991). Here, the pre- and post-failure nonlinear behaviour was addressed within the framework of rate-independent theory of orthotropic plasticity and under plane stress assumptions; viscous effects were not considered. A quadratic criterion for the plastic yield was used, and the plastic surface was assumed to be similar in tension or compression. To predict failure, the Tsai-Hill criterion was used for the unidirectional case, along with an associated flow rule. This model was later extended to predict the nonlinear response of fibre-reinforced composite laminates using a failure criterion of the same functional (quadratic) form of the yield criterion, replacing the yield stresses by the ultimate stresses (Vaziri, et al., 1992).

To predict the inelastic response of fibre-reinforced polymer composites with unidirectional reinforcements, a smeared crack model has been proposed (Camanho, et

al., 2013), which assumes an additive decomposition of the strain tensor into elastic, plastic and cracking strains, and can therefore account for the elastic-plastic behaviour prior to the onset of fracture when coupled with an elastic-plastic model (Vogler, et al., 2013). The model uses only independently measured, ply-based material properties, with no need of '*inverse identification*' relying on model parameters that are adjusted until the finite element analyses match the experimental tests. Good agreement was obtained for the predictions of the plastic deformation, of the propagation of damage, and of the final failure of composite materials subjected to off-axis tensile and compressive loadings, and of multidirectional laminates with centrally located sharp notches and circular holes. Nevertheless, these results were limited to quasi-static conditions.

To account for viscoplasticity, an additive decomposition of the elastic and the plastic part of the strain rate was proposed earlier (Gates & Sun, 1991) and (Yoon & Sun, 1991), based on a previous elastic-plastic flow rule (Sun & Chen, 1989), and applied to thermoplastic-based composites. The model is based on the Perzyna (Perzyna, 1963) overstress function to express the plastic strain rate, and on a power law with two parameters to link the effective plastic strain rate and the overstress. This model, however, did not account for the viscous effect in the elastic domain (viscoelasticity).

More recently, a fully three-dimensional elastic-plastic model (Vogler, et al., 2013) was also extended to take into account the observed strain-rate dependency in the plastic response based on the Perzyna (Perzyna, 1963) overstress function (Koerber, et al., 2018), and applied to carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy. However, the proposed viscoplastic model relied on scaling functions to model the experimentally observed viscoelastic behaviour. This solution was considered a limiting factor of the proposed model, and therefore a new fully three-dimensional transversely isotropic viscoelastic-viscoplastic model was proposed (Gerbaud, et al., 2019), which considers the viscous effects and the non-linearities prior to the onset of cracking. This model was formulated using the small deformation theory, following an additive decomposition of the strain tensor into its viscoelastic and viscoplastic parts. The viscoelastic extension was based on a generalised Maxwell model (Kaliske & Rothert, 1997) and (Kaliske, 2000) and the viscoplastic part used a non-associative flow rule and the Perzyna (Perzyna, 1963) type overstress model. Although this model was validated on a carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy system, it includes the necessary ingredients for application in the next generation of thermoplastic composites. However, the small deformation setting in which it is based may not be suitable for thermoplastic-based composites, which are expected to exhibit larger deformations prior to damage initiation. Moreover, it has not been coupled yet with a damage model to represent the material response after damage initiation.

In fact, a limited number of studies have addressed the inelastic response of fibre-reinforced thermoplastic-based composites after damage initiation. The available contributions often use constitutive models and discretisation techniques previously developed for fibre-reinforced thermosetting composites, coupled (Liu, et al., 2020) or not (Bouvet, et al., 2018) with a plasticity model or just a nonlinear shear model (Tan & Falzon, 2016) and (Tan & Falzon, 2016). The viscous effects, prior or after damage initiation, are often neglected. However, it is clear that the effect of the strain rate on the

material properties, including the fracture toughness (Bouvet, et al., 2018), is essential to obtain good predictions of the mechanical response of thermoplastic-based composites under dynamic events (e.g. low-velocity impact), something not observed for thermosetting composites. This effect has so far been accounted for simply by scaling the properties (e.g. the fracture toughness (Bouvet, et al., 2018)) based on the measured values for different loading rates, or fitting to the experimental data for selected cases. Improved models need to account for these effects in their formulations, fed by independently measured material properties obtained from reliable characterisation static and dynamic testing protocols. Detailed verification and validation of these models must be performed to ensure their reliability and robustness for integration into virtual testing platforms. These two aspects have not been fully covered yet, neither separately nor together, in the prediction of the mechanical response of thermoplastic-based composites.

4. Concluding remarks

This report shows that there is the need to continue the development of constitutive models that can accurately capture the pre- and post-failure mechanical response of thermoplastic-based composites. In particular, the following features are yet to be covered:

- *Linking the processing conditions – composite consolidation and degree of crystallinity of the thermoplastic matrix – and the mechanical response of the thermoplastic composite.* An appropriate coupling between process simulation, crystallisation kinetics (Chelaghma, 2018) and mechanical simulation are required to address this point. Alternatively, well-defined characterisation protocols should be established, and applied in the determination of the mechanical properties for the processing conditions of interest, while ensuring that the latter is accurately controlled.
- *Extending the three-dimensional viscoelastic/viscoplastic models (Gerbaud, et al., 2019) to a finite deformation setting.* Due to the important viscoelastic/viscoplastic deformation modes, thermoplastic-based composites are expected to exhibit large deformations prior to damage initiation. A small deformation setting will pose a strong limitation to the application of these models in general loading conditions and geometries.
- *Coupling between three-dimensional viscoelastic/viscoplastic models (Gerbaud, et al., 2019) and (time-dependent) damage models to predict the post-localisation inelastic behaviour of thermoplastic-based composites.* Advanced failure criteria (Camanho, et al., 2015) combined with continuum damage mechanics (Furtado, et al., 2019) or smeared crack models (Zhuang, et al., 2019) provide a sound solution to the prediction of damage initiation and propagation in thermoplastics composites. However, extension to a finite deformation setting and an accurate representation of the time-dependent strengths and fracture toughness are yet to be included in such frameworks. In addition, reliable test protocols should be established for the characterisation of the sensitivity to the loading rates of the strength (Koerber, et al., 2018), interlaminar (Smiley & Pipes, 1987) and intralaminar fracture toughness (Kuhn, et al., 2017) and (Kuhn, et al., 2018).
- *Accounting for temperature-dependent behaviour.* Thermoplastic-based materials are more sensitive to the surrounding temperature than thermosetting composites, and, for certain applications, accounting for the temperature-dependent behaviour of the thermoplastic material will be crucial for an accurate representation of its mechanical response.
- *Understanding the effect of strain-rate sensitivity on the structural response and design allowables.* Understand the difference between thermoplastic- and thermoset-based composites under quasi-static and dynamic loading (e.g. low velocity impact damage and residual strength) for alternative thermoplastic composite systems (e.g. PEKK in UD tape format).

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